

A Diagnostic Accountability of the Proportional Contribution Rate of Extent of Biophysical Processes of Desertification and the Landscape Changes in the Drylands of North Eastern Zone of Nigeria

Christopher Ndabula

Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State, Nigeria

Kehinde Taofik Oyatayo

Kwararafa University, Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

Godwill G. Jidauna

Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State, Nigeria

Suggested Citation

Ndabula, C., Oyatayo, K.T., & Jidauna, G.G. (2024). A Diagnostic Accountability of the Proportional Contribution Rate of Extent of Biophysical Processes of Desertification and the Landscape Changes in the Drylands of North Eastern Zone of Nigeria. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(5), 109-126.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(5\).11](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(5).11)

Abstract:

So much in literature has been reported on the complex nature of desertification processes, and extents, but very little is known about the proportional contribution rate of these processes in a given landscape and hence the ultimate aim of this study. RS/GIS change detection techniques was employed in the landscape change analysis. The natural jenks classification in the spatial analyst tool in ArGIS was used to evaluate and map the landscape sensitivity areas. Twelve specific indicators representing specific processes and effects were analysed and three aggregated to represent four types of landscape; vegetation, soil, hydro-geomorphic and micro-climatic. A total of 8923km² (29%) of the Vegetation landscape showed either positive or negative changes in vegetation cover. Low sensitivity areas contributed the highest (40.2%), followed by very high (4.6%), moderate (2.6%) and very low (2.5%) of vegetation degradation. 50% of the landscape recorded vegetation degradation while the other 50% recorded regeneration of vegetation. A very large extent (70.5%) of the soil landscape experienced either positive or negative soil changes. Soil degradation was contributed by Moderate (26.4%), High (17.8%), Low (5%) sensitivity landscapes. About 50% of the soil landscape revealed various forms of degradation. Only a small extent of the hydro-geomorphic landscape (7.8%) of the landscape underwent changes either positive (degradation) or negative (recovery). Out of this extent the very high sensitivity class contributed 32.1%, while moderate (14.5%) and Very Low (3.4%) of degradation. The pattern of contributions of changes in extents in the micro-climatic landscape indicated only a small extent of the landscape (9.6%). The high sensitivity landscape alone contributed 31.6% of the areas that observed degradation, followed by very high (10.1%) and Moderate (8.3%), this put together a total of 50% of the landscape recorded degradation.

Keywords: *Biophysical Processes, Desertification, land degradation and Landscape Changes.*

Introduction

Land degradation (LD) is one of the major environmental degradation all over the world. It is the Cinderella of Global Environmental and Climate Change (Grainger *et al.*, 2000). It is a complex, pervasive process that drives the loss or decline in land or all terrestrial ecosystems functions and services. Desertification is a significant universal ecological catastrophe (Braganza, 2022). Deserts are amid "fragile dryland ecosystems" which are widely recognized to be prone to desertification. It has been estimated that approximately 10–20% of drylands are already degraded, the total area affected by desertification being between 6 and 12 million square kilometres, that about 1–6% of the inhabitants of drylands live in desertified areas, and that a billion people are under threat from further desertification. Desertification involves the process of depletion of terrestrial resources of a comparatively dry area in becoming gradually arid.

Desertification involves multiple causal factors including climatic, biophysical and anthropogenic but with context specific solutions (Reynolds, *et al.*, 2002; IPBES 2018a;). Conacher and Sala (1998) gave a broader sense of land degradation which they defined as an "alteration to all aspects of the natural or biophysical environment due to climatic variations and human actions to the detriment of vegetation, soils, landforms, water and ecosystems". Ndabula (2015) simply put it as the adverse alteration of the eco-geomorphic landscape comprising the elements of vegetation, soil, hydro-geomorphic and micro-climatic. So much work in the literature have been focused on causes and processes of desertification. The number of desertification processes is large and they are extensively covered in the reports of (IPBES, 2018a; Lal, 2016; Racine, 2008; UNCCD, 2017). Geist *et al.*, 2004; Reynolds *et al.*, 2007)

Desertification Processes

In so far as desertification is thought to mean 'land degradation', it is commonly believed that the term refers essentially to a problem of faster-than-normal degradation of the land, which

takes place when the land surface processes found under natural conditions are accelerated due to climatic perturbations or increased human pressures (the driving forces that ultimately trigger degradation). While desertification processes are clubbed together under 'biophysical', there are also the 'socio-economic' processes that aid in the exacerbation of the normal rates of degradation.

Bio-physical Processes

The extent and degree of desertification can be assessed indirectly by using selected indicators (Rajan *et al.* 2010; Kosmos *et al.* 2015). It has been reported that the indicators of desertification are mostly climate, soil, vegetation and management factors (Kosmas *et al.* 1999; Sivakumar 2007). The major biophysical factors responsible for soil erosion, salinisation/alkalinisation, vegetal degradation and deterioration of soil fertility are collected from previous studies (Rajan *et al.* 2010; Naidu *et al.* 2014; Kosmos *et al.* 2015) and waterlogging. It is also recognised that acceleration of these processes is important, rather than the normal rates of their functioning. Dregne (1991) recommended that the status of these processes should be monitored in rain-fed croplands, irrigated croplands and rangelands. Since desertification is regarded to be site specific it therefore suggest that while mapping the distribution of the areas affected by the different processes, it is usual to consider one dominant process to one affected area.

Biophysical indicators are described with respect to the soil properties (e.g., soil fertility, soil productivity, compaction, and loss of topsoil and subsoil); erosion (e.g., shifting sands over fertile soils, water turbidity and sedimentation, soil loss, and gully incidence), and land form (e.g. topography) (Snel and Bot, 2002). Ustin *et al.* (2005) has shown that information related to many of the biophysical indicators can be extracted from satellite imagery and presented a review of spectral characteristics of plants and soils that are detectable using optical sensors and methods to identify and quantify properties that have the potential for monitoring arid degradation processes and landscape changes.

Socio-economic Processes

Compared to the bio-physical processes, the socio-economic factors have received less attention, especially because the analysis involves a very large size of sample population and, while the information can be gathered mostly through inter-personal dialogues using some standard questionnaire, the process is time-consuming, needs large human-hours to gather the data at sample household to village levels, and is often costly. Even then the level of quantification that can be achieved with conviction for bio-physical variables, in a shorter period of time and at pixel level, can hardly be achieved at any comparable scale or resolution for socio-economic variables. Some socio-economic indicators, such as changes in land use and herd composition, utilization of fuel wood, local perceptions, etc., were provided by Dregne (1983). Socioeconomic variables such as population density, population growth rate also has been included by some of the researchers as a potential indicator for assessment of desertification (Salvati et al. 2011 and Salvati and Zitti 2008).

Due to the key role of poverty as a root cause, and the respective consequences which prove that LDD is more pronounced among the poorest segments of the world population, socioeconomic indicators are framed by key characteristics of poverty: lack of opportunity (e.g., lack of income, credit, land, and other assets of attaining basic necessities such as food, clothing and shelter); insecurity (e.g., vulnerability to adverse shocks and limited means to cope); and disempowerment (e.g., voicelessness and powerless to influence decisions) (Snel and Bot, 2002).

Land Degradation sets in once this balance is upset, and soil, water and vegetation – the basic elements of land are damaged, as manifested in processes such Soil loses of topsoil by erosion and some essential nutrients (thus developing nutrient imbalances), accumulates harmful chemicals by salinization, alkalization or acidification, or develops physical deformities such as compaction or textural discontinuity in the profile including hard pan formation. Water

accumulates close to or above the soil surface (waterlogging) or becomes scanty (desiccation) or salty. Other form of degradation include Vegetation loses of productivity of useful plants due to systematic deforestation, invasion by shrubs or less useful species.

While the causes of desertification are both biophysical and socio-economic, the processes or actual mechanisms of land degradation are revealed on the biophysical. These processes are classified under broad categories of degradation of physical, chemical and biological properties of terrestrial ecosystems or landscape. In fact Symeonakis and Drake (2004) clearly asserted that the processes of desertification will penultimately end in vegetation degradation and finally culminate in soil degradation.

Considering the complexities involved in the degradation processes, more definitive studies are required to segregate the signatures of human-induced degradation from the natural ones hence the reason for the focus of this study on biophysical processes and effects. Considering that many bio-physical indicators can develop from a variety of causes, it is difficult to prejudge the features and link them to a particular pressure indicator. Notwithstanding Stocking and Murnaghan (2000) have listed many field indicators of degradation, and simple methods for measuring them. Surface manifestation of some physical and chemical processes of degradation, such as waterlogging and salinization due to over-use of irrigation, is now easy from remote sensing, (Kar et al., 2009, 2016).

This study adopted the eco-geomorphic approach to study desertification (Mueller *et al*, 2007; Turnbull *et al.*, 2008).

The basic principles of eco-geomorphology employed in this study were;

- ‘Cause-effect’ or ‘process-form’ ‘structure-function’ or ‘exposure-sensitivity’ relationships were used for symptomatic diagnosis of land degradation process through a well selected biophysical indicators.

- The application of the uniformitarian doctrine of ‘Present is key to the past’ was used in the interpretation and field based description of spatio-temporal patterns of the status of desertification judging from the current status.
- The highlight in the definition of desertification by Conacher and Sala (1998) and (Ndabula 2015)) which gave a broader sense of land degradation as the “alteration to all aspects of the natural (or biophysical) environment”.

The major theoretical base of the methodology used in this study is the application of hierarchy theory for environmental sensitivity analysis to depict desertification patterns that recognise the structural and functional hierarchical nature of both ecologic and geomorphic systems and which actually determine the dynamic rate and intensity of desertification. This is the best way the spatio-temporal patterns of desertification status can be understood better.

This study identified with one problem that in most desertification assessment studies based on landuse/landcover approach, emphasis has been on rate, extent and intensity with practically little or no attention to proportional contribution to these changes.

Landscape patterns often reveals the occurrence of LD and can be analysed and interpreted in terms of landsue/landcover change ‘trajectories’. Geist and Lambin (2006) proposed to apply the notion of syndrome to the more specific field of

LULC trajectories. They suggest that the apparent complexity in land use change processes can be summarized in a limited number of ways in which these causes interact. The 'syndrome' approach has been used to describe complex interactive processes and symptoms which appear variously and in many places in typical combinations and patterns. The notion of syndrome has been extended to LD and desertification processes.

Figure 1. Eco-Geomorphic Framework

Study Area

The study area is a strip of the dryland landscape that cuts between Yobe-Borno and covers Lat. 10° 15' - 13° 20'N and Long. 10°50' – 12°10' E

Figure 2. Desertification Frontline State Showing Study Area
Source: FU Dutsinma GIS Lab.

The semi-arid zone of Nigeria covers the dry-sub-humid (sudan savanna) and the sahel savanna occupying approximately 78% (720, 902 km²) of the total landmass of Nigeria (Odjugo and Ikhuoria, 200). The region is ecologically referred to as sudano-sahelian zone. Climatologically classified into the (Koppen's Aw and As). It is dirminantly under the prevailing hot dry Tropical Continental air mass (cT) during the dry season (Nov – March/April) (Osaigbovo, 2000).

The vegetation type is tropical savanna and sahel in the northernmost part. Which are the areas highly prone to desertification. The soils are largely the weakly, developed regosols which are

loose, excessively drained and intensely leached with little evidence of pedogenesis hence range between azonal and intra-zonal soils. Except in the sokoto and chad basins where these desert sand deposits have been subjected to greater pedogenesis giving rise to the brown and reddish grown soils (Areola, 1982). Ferruginous and ferrisols predominate in all other parts with exception of areas around Lake Chad and major rivers where riverine and lacustrine type of hydromorphic soils are found.

Materials and Methods

Table 1. Required Materials

Data type	Source	Purpose
Climatic data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature Rainfall 	Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NIMET), Lagos	Evaluation of potential evapo-transpiration (PET) and the generation of both rainfall/PET surfaces, and finally for evaluation and mapping of aridity index (AI)
Multi-temporal Satellite images (landsat.TM,(1990), Landsat. ETM (2000 and 2010) and OLI/TIR (2020))	National Airspace Research Development Agency (NASRDA), Abuja, National Center for Remote Sensing (NCRS), Jos	Evaluation and mapping using spectral indices representing specific elements of desertification processes and landscapes
Digital Elevation Model (DEM)	National Center for Remote Sensing (NCRS), Jos	Evaluation of hydro-geomorphic indices
Relevant spatial thematic maps such as topomaps, geology and soil maps, administrative , map of weather station distribution	Ahmadu Bello University's map library, NCRS, Jos and online sources	Field reconnaissance, classification and interpretation of images and raster maps generated

Methodology

The study employed an eco-geomorphic approach using a 3-level analysis

- i. Analysis of specific elements of land degradation processes
- ii. Analysis of specific components of the landscape
- iii. Analysis of the complex landscape
- iv. Analysis of Landscape sensitivity areas and their proportional contribution rate

- v. Analysis of extents of landscape changes and proportional contribution rate of desertification processes and landscapes.

Analysis of Specific Processes of Desertification and Selection of Indicators

This study adopted the Remote Sensing Based Assessment of Biophysical Indicators for Land Degradation and Desertification by Ustin et., al (2005). All the indicators selected applied spectral indices for landscape change detection.

A total of twelve (12) indicators representing specific land degradation processes were used and evaluated using RS spectral indices.

Note also that most of the indicators selected have the potential to be proxy to more than one process.

The selected indices are as follows;

Soil:

Soil Brightness Index (SBI) = Soil Organic Matter or soil organic carbon loss

Topsoil Grain size Index (GSI) = Top Soil Coarsening or hard pan development

Soil Crusting Index (SCI) = structural soil crusts

Vegetation:

Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) = Changes in woody tree cover greenness

Absorbed Photosynthetic Active Radiation (APAR) = Invasion by Shrubs

Photosynthetic Reflectance Index = Changes in Photosynthesis efficiency.

Micro-climatic:

Aridity Index (AI) = decreasing rainfall amounts, dry spells and Droughts

Land Surface Albedo (LSA) = increasing landscape reflectance due to sandification and vegetation cover loss

Land Surface Temperature (LST) = increasing land surface temperature due to loss of forest

The three (3) micro-climatic indices are well related in the complex bio-geophysical feedback mechanism in the semi-arid landscape.

Hydro-geomorphic:

Topographic Wetness Index (TWI) = loss of wetlands and soil moisture retention or desiccation

Stream power Index (SPI) = development of rills and gullies

Sediment Transport Index (STI) = water erosion or sediment loss.

Analysis of Specific Landscape Components and Aggregation of into Composite Index for Specific Components of the Landscape

Three of each of these twelve were selected to represent vegetation, soil, hydro-geomorphic and micro-climatic landscapes respectively (3-processes X 4 landscape components of the overall complex dryland landscape)

Analysis of Landscape Sensitivity Areas and Their Proportional Contribution Rates

Segmentation of landscape into various sensitivity areas as in line with environmentally sensitive land area index by (Symeonakis et al., 2016). The stretch values of the evaluated specific indices as proxy for processes and composite indices were classified using the natural Jenks in the spatial analyst tool in ArcGIS.

This approach recognises the multiplicity of specific processes and complexity of the interactions of processes of desertification. It also agrees with the criticism of using single indicators for assessment of desertification such as Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) by (Piao et al., 2005), drought-tolerant plant species (An et al., 2007), grass cover (Bestmeyer et al., 2013), land productivity dynamics (Baskan et al., 2017), ecosystem net primary productivity (Zhou et al., 2015) and Aridity Index (AI) by (Feng and Fu, 2013; Zarch et al., 2015; Ji et al., 2015; Spinoni et al., 2015; Huang et al., 2016; Ramarao et al., 2018). Hence the single indicators in this approach only represent specific processes. Their aggregation to assess desertification in the complex landscape therefore conforms with the opinion of (Prince, 2016; Cherlet et al., 2018) in their studies.

Analysis of Extents of Landscape Changes and Proportional Contribution Rate of Desertification Processes and Landscapes

Landuse/landcover change detection techniques have been used to examine the spatio-temporal patterns of changes in extents of land degradation but rarely do they examine the proportional contributions of these changes by the different factors applied.

Landscape Proportional contribution of rate of

change: Is contribution rate of landscape change in relation to total change of all other landscapes (Wang, 2010) was adopted for this study.

$$A_i = U_{bi} - U_{ai} / \sum(U_{bi} - U_{ai}) \quad (1)$$

Where;

A_i = the proportional contribution rate of a particular landcover class in relation to the total change of all the landcover classes

U_{ai} = Areal extent of landcover at the beginning of study

U_{bi} = Areal extent of landcover at the end of study

Results and Discussion

From Table 2. It reveals that about 68% (20725 km²) of the landscape under review contributed to various forms and rates of changes in the woody trees landscape. Highest loss (45%) followed by 3.7% were recorded in the very low and very high sensitivity vegetation landscape. On the other hand the highest positive or increase rate (39%) was recorded in the Moderate followed by low (10%) and least (0.2%) by High sensitivity vegetation landscape areas. The observation of increasing greenness in high, moderate and low sensitivity areas agrees with several other studies (Fensholt et al., 2012; Andela et al., 2013) the the semi-arid are becoming greener according to satellite observations. Ecosystem function and services are maximized under moderate levels of woody plant cover. Therefore areas undergoing loss of woody trees cover are thus experiencing declining ecosystem function and services (4).

Table 2. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on NDVI

Landscape Sensitivity Area (ESA)	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in km ² 1990 (U_{ai})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km ² 2000	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km ² :2020 (U_{bi})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km ² based on NDVSI (U_{bi1})	Change in extent of i^{th} SA in Km ² for study period ($U_{bi} - U_{ai}$)	Proportion of contribution by i^{th} class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	856	92	81	3	-775	-3.70
2- High	45	10876	82	857	37	0.20
3- Moderate	9655	19081	17896	8878	8241	39.80
4- Low	9708	58	11977	9665	2269	10.90
5- Very low	10109	266	706	10969	-9403	-45.40
Total Area	30373	30373		30373	$\Sigma = 20725$	100.00

Table 3. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on APAR

Landscape Sensitivity Area (ESA)	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in km ² 1990 (U_{ai})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km ² 2000	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km ² :2020 (U_{bi})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km ² based on NDVSI (U_{bi1})	Change in extent of i^{th} SA in Km ² for study period ($U_{bi} - U_{ai}$)	Proportion of contribution by i^{th} class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	8612	14531	6569	778	-2043	-23.80
2- High	10727	12566	12418	1942	1691	19.70
3- Moderate	6723	1624	11038	21687	4315	50.40
4- Low	421	1026	234	5858	-187	-2.20
5- Very low	445	626	111	115	-334	-3.90
Total Area	26928	30373	30373	30373	$\Sigma = 8570$	100.00

Both primary productivity and shrubiness were analysed using APAR, the results in Table 3. Shows that the highest rate of shrub invasion (50%) was contributed by the moderate class followed by High sensitivity class (19.70%). In the Very high, Low and very low sensitivity vegetation landscape shrub invasion decreased

by 23.8%, 2.2% and 1.9% respectively. A total of 8570km² of the study area recorded extension in shrub landscape. Shrub invasion in a dryland landscape has been used as one of the signs of declining ecosystem function and land degradation (Eldridge & Soliveres, 2014; Barbosa da Silva et al., 2016)

Table 4. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on PRI

Landscape Sensitivity Area (ESA)	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in km ² 1990 (U _{ai})	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² 2000	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² :2020 (U _{bi})	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² based on NDVSI (U _{bi1})	Change in extent of ⁱ th SA in Km ² for study period (U _{bi} -U _{ai})	Proportion of contribution by ⁱ th class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	15	13	17	1168	2	0.00
2- High	4462	4098	376	4603	-4086	-22.80
3- Moderate	6272	9691	5170	6773	-1102	-6.10
4- Low	8625	11218	17587	5900	8962	50.00
5- Very low	10999	5353	7223	11929	-3776	-21.10
Total Area	30373	30373	30373	30373	∑ = 17928	100.00

Photosynthetic Reflectance Index (PRI), that is sensitive to changing xanthophylls cycle pigments. They successfully used this method to estimate photosynthetic efficiency. Styliniski et al.

showed that the PRI could track seasonal changes in carotenoid pigments and photosynthetic activity of mature semiarid evergreen shrubs.

Table 5. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on SBI

Landscape Sensitivity Area (ESA)	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in km ² 1990 (U _{ai})	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² 2000	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² :2020 (U _{bi})	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² based on NDVSI (U _{bi1})	Change in extent of ⁱ th SA in Km ² for study period (U _{bi} -U _{ai})	Proportion of contribution by ⁱ th class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	4006	3352	2005	3309	-2001	-14.8
2- High	5565	5992	5743	5061	178	1.3
3- Moderate	9305	5620	8684	6450	-621	-4.6
4- Low	2347	9324	8351	6463	6004	44.4
5- Very low	10310	6084	5589	9089	-4721	-34.9
Total Area	30373	30373	30373	30373	∑ = 13525	100.00

Organic matter is closely related to soil quality and degradation processes in natural vegetation and agricultural lands. It is not only an indicator of soil degradation, but also regulating other

biogeochemical processes. Aranda and Oyonarte (2005) found lowest quality soil organic matter under degraded shrubs suggesting that degraded vegetation may lead to soil degradation

Table 6. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on SCI

Landscape Sensitivity Areas (SA)	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in km^2 1990 (U_{ai})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 2000	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 :2020 (U_{bi})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 based on NDVSI (U_{bi1})	Change in extent of i^{th} SA in Km^2 for study period ($U_{bi}-U_{ai}$)	Proportion of contribution by i^{th} class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	1834	123	82	104	-1752	-10.1
2- High	3540	1687	3350	1890	-190	-1.1
3- Moderate	5997	12087	9396	3921	3399	19.5
4- Low	7448	1	13749	6088	6301	36.2
5- Very low	11552	6476	5768	16369	-5784	-33.2
Total Area	30373	30373	30373	30374	$\Sigma = 17426$	100.00

Weathering process that soils undergo in arid and semiarid regions are related primarily to high temperatures and low and/or irregular rainfall. Thus, salt dissolution combined with high evaporation can precipitate alkaline salts to form hardpans at the wetting front. Important soil surface processes are due to the combination of

irregular precipitation events, shallow soil development, and scarce vegetative cover which create low infiltration capacity and high runoff. . Biological and structural soil crusts have very different properties in terms of soil health (Goldshleger, et al., 2001).

Table 7. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on GSI

Landscape Sensitivity Areas (SA)	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in km^2 1990 (U_{ai})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 2000	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 :2020 (U_{bi})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 based on NDVSI (U_{bi1})	Change in extent of i^{th} SA in Km^2 for study period ($U_{bi}-U_{ai}$)	Proportion of contribution by i^{th} class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	703	4956	427	452	-276	-1.2
2- High	7268	7938	8420	7440	1152	5.1
3- Moderate	6883	2397	14221	6575	7338	32.6
4- Low	5058	160	7170	5014	2112	9.4
5- Very low	11770	14921	136	10921	-11634	-51.7
Total Area	30373	30373	30373	30373	$\Sigma = 22512$	100.00

Results of topsoil coarsening in Table 7. Shows that a very vast extent (74%) experienced changes in fine sand distribution. The moderate sensitivity area contributed to increase in topsoil coarsening by (32.6%) followed by Low (9.4%)

and High (5.1%). On the other hand the process of topsoil coarsening declined in the Very low sensitivity areas which contributed (51.7) and very high (1.2%).

Table 8. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on TWI

Landscape Sensitivity Areas (SA)	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in km^2 1990 (U_{ai})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 2000	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 :2020 (U_{bi})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 based on NDVSI (U_{bi1})	Change in extent of i^{th} SA in Km^2 for study period ($U_{bi}-U_{ai}$)	Proportion of contribution by i^{th} class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	17927	17976	18007	18090	80	18.3
2- High	5170	5109	5250	5116	80	18.3
3- Moderate	4374	4346	4246	4239	-128	-29.2
4- Low	1944	1916	1853	1918	-91	-20.80
5- Very low	957	1025	1016	1007	59	13.5
Total Area	30372	30373	30373	30373	$\Sigma = 438$	100.00

Changes in extent of areas that showed variation in TWI in the landscape is very small (438 km² or 1.4%). TWI was used as an indicator of both soil moisture condition and wetland degradation. The results in Table 8. Is a clear indication that the rate of soil desiccation and loss of wetlands are highest (18.3%) in both the very high and high sensitivity areas followed by very low areas (13.5%). On the other hand both moderate and low sensitivity landscape showed recovery in wetlands and soil moisture conditions at the rates of 29.2 and 20.8% respectively. Aguilera et al (2013) reported the hydrological behaviour of

the anthropized semi-arid wetland of Las Tablas de Daimiel National Park (Spain). Similarly, Aguilera et al. (2016) also predicted changes in soil conditions in the Mediterranean semi-arid region of Moreno, Spain. These implies that anthropogenic activities such as cultivation, grazing, bush burning and droughts are associated in soil or wetlands desiccation and hence land degradation (Finlayson & Rea 1999). Dada et al., (2007) reported wetland loss through erosion and conversion to alternative land uses in South Africa.

Table 9. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on SPI

Landscape Sensitivity Areas (SA)	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in km ² 1990 (U _{ai})	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² 2000	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² :2020 (U _{bi})	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² based on NDVSI (U _{bi1})	Change in extent of ⁱ th SA in Km ² for study period (U _{bi} -U _{ai})	Proportion of contribution by ⁱ th class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	17730	17733	17698	17778	-32	-25.4
2- High	4693	4583	4670	4543	-23	-18.3
3- Moderate	4566	4581	4569	4575	3	2.4
4- Low	2283	2331	2342	2362	59	46.8
5- Very low	1100	1137	1091	1114	-9	-7.1
Total Area	30373	30373	30373	30373	Σ = 126	100.00

As shown in Table 9. Changes in rills, gullies and streams channels was in a total extent of 126 km² during the entire period. Most of the positive changes was contributed by the Low sensitivity landscape (46.8%) followed by Moderate (2.4%). Negative contributions were recorded in the very high (25.4%), High (18.3%) and Very low (7.1%). This could mean that most of rills and gullies are transient and easily covered by sand following erosion.

In the semi-arid areas, rill and gully erosion usually takes place in pulses of fast advancement, separated by years with almost no advancement (Poesen et al., 1996). The processes are activated during periods of high-intensity above-normal rainfall. A good vegetation cover can minimize the rate of advancement of rill and gully heads, but under a constantly degrading environment it is difficult to say if land use during a particular

period can be held responsible for the measured advancement. It is most likely that rainfall amount and rainfall intensity will determine the rate of rill and gully formation, while the sites of their occurrences may be linked to fractures and other weaker zones within the sediments, as well as geologically recent mild tectonic events (Kar, 1993a).

STI was applied in this study as a proxy of water erosion in the study area. The results as presented in Table 10. Revealed that the very high sensitivity areas contributed the highest (49.8%) of sediment transported in the 5044 km² of landscape extent which recorded change in sediment transport with the moderate class least (0.2%). Negative change in erosion areas was recorded in High (40.7%), Low (5.7%) and very low (3.6%) of sensitivity erosional landscape respectively.

Table 10. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on STI

Landscape Sensitivity Areas (SA)	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in km^2 1990 (U_{ai})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 2000	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in $Km^2:2020$ (U_{bi})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 based on NDVSI (U_{bi1})	Change in extent of i^{th} SA in Km^2 for study period ($U_{bi}-U_{ai}$)	Proportion of contribution by i^{th} class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	10608	11932	11932	13118	2510	49.8
2- High	8650	7764	7764	6599	-2051	-40.7
3- Moderate	4985	4875	4875	4997	12	0.2
4- Low	4248	4031	4031	3960	-288	-5.7
5- Very low	1881	1769	1769	1698	-183	-3.6
Total Area	30373	30373	30373	30373	$\Sigma = 5044$	100.00

Table 11. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on ASI

Landscape Sensitivity Areas (SA)	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in km^2 1990 (U_{ai})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 2000	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in $Km^2:2020$ (U_{bi})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 based on NDVSI (U_{bi1})	Change in extent of i^{th} SA in Km^2 for study period ($U_{bi}-U_{ai}$)	Proportion of contribution by i^{th} class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	6647	7038	6598	8116	1469	20.7
2- High	7217	7066	6610	9132	1915	26.9
3- Moderate	5455	5677	6579	5625	170	2.4
4- Low	5439	5520	5701	4012	-1427	-20.1
5- Very low	5613	5071	4882	3486	-2127	-29.9
Total Area	30372	30372	30373	30372	$\Sigma = 7108$	100.00

Aridity and drought have been considered to major indicators of desertification. Therefore the aridity index is used as a proxy for drought and aridity. From results in Table 11. It indicates that the extent of the studied landscape that responded to changes in aridity is 7108 over the period of review. Out of this extent the high, very high and moderate sensitivity areas contributed positively 26.9, 20.7 and 2.4% respectively to increasing aridification. On the other hand very low and low sensitivity areas

recorded negative or decreasing extent of areas sensitive to aridity. Similar reports on drought and aridity Nigerian semi-arid region have been presented by Medugu et al., (2011) and Fabeku and Faleyimu (2017). : semi-arid ecosystems are by definition limited by water. Low but highly variable precipitation, often with unpredictable periodicity, dominates the responses of desert ecosystems. Fractional cover, biomass and leaf area are generally proportional to precipitation and available soil moisture (Renolds et al., 2004).

Table 12. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on LSA

Landscape Sensitivity Areas (SA)	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in km^2 1990 (U_{ai})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 2000	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in $Km^2:2020$ (U_{bi})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 based on NDVSI (U_{bi1})	Change in extent of i^{th} SA in Km^2 for study period ($U_{bi}-U_{ai}$)	Proportion of contribution by i^{th} class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	4317	3459	4007	4742	-310	-3.1
2- High	7018	6384	8738	7398	1720	17.3
3- Moderate	7204	5149	10464	7113	3260	32.7
4- Low	7018	14960	6636	6932	-382	-3.8
5- Very low	4816	420	527	4187	-4289	-43.1
Total Area	3072	3072	3072	3073	$\Sigma = 9961$	100.00

Changes in land surface albedo for a long term have been used to assessed land degradation or desertification especially is dryland areas. The outcome of changes in extent of albedo in the study area showed a total extent of 9961km² (33%) of the landscape under review. Results in Table 12. Above indicates that highest positive

contribution rate (32.7%) was observed in the moderate sensitivity landscape followed by high (17.3%). Exgtent of landscape that revealed negative contribution rate was observed in the very low (43.1%), Low (3.8%) and very high sensitivity landscape (3.1%).

Table 13. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on LST

Landscape Sensitivity Areas (SA)	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in km ² 1990 (U _{ai})	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² 2000	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² :2020 (U _{bi})	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² based on NDVSI (U _{bi1})	Change in extent of ⁱ th SA in Km ² for study period (U _{bi} -U _{ai})	Proportion of contribution by ⁱ th class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	7048	6600	7458	5024	410	4.6
2- High	15079	1048	10615	6328	-4464	-50
3- Moderate	7522	5025	7753	4936	231	2.6
4- Low	211	6690	3802	3111	3591	40.2
5- Very low	517	2321	744	10,075	227	2.5
Total Area	30380	30373	30373	30373	Σ = 8923	100.00

Table 14. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on VSI

Landscape Sensitivity Areas (SA)	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in km ² 1990 (U _{ai})	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² 2000	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² :2020 (U _{bi})	Extent of ⁱ th class of SA in Km ² based on NDVSI (U _{bi1})	Change in extent of ⁱ th SA in Km ² for study period (U _{bi} -U _{ai})	Proportion of contribution by ⁱ th class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	856	16160	6893	6037	-158.5	4.6
2- High	9901	13762	13199	3298	-8265	-50
3- Moderate	9479	98	7779	-1700	-728.5	2.6
4- Low	5006	139	1915	-3091	4378.5	40.2
5- Very low	5131	213	586	-4545	4774	2.5
Total Area	30373	30373	30373	30373	Σ = 8923	100.00

Very interesting patterns of degradation in the vegetation landscape were observed. A total of 8923km² of the landscape showed either positive or negative changes in vegetation cover. As can be seen in Table 14. The high vegetation landscape sensitivity area contribuyed 50% of decreasing trends of vegetation cover loss. This represent vegetation regeneration probably due to afforestation efforts over the period. However, positive or otherwise increasing vegetation cover lost was recorded in the other

sensitivity landscape with Low areas being the highest (40.2%), followed by very high (4.6%), moderate (2.6%) and very low (2.5%).

In summary the distribution of observation of changes in the vegetation landscape implies that 50% of the landscape recorded vegetation degradation while the other 50% recorded regeneration of vegetation and all of which occurred in the high sensitivity landscape.

Table 15. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on SSI

Landscape Sensitivity Areas (SA)	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in km^2 1990 (U_{ai})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 2000	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in $Km^2:2020$ (U_{bi})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 based on NDVSI (U_{bi1})	Change in extent of i^{th} SA in Km^2 for study period ($U_{bi}-U_{ai}$)	Proportion of contribution by i^{th} class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	2903	1689	3068	1570	165	0.8
2- High	3637	6069	7449	3255	3812	17.8
3- Moderate	6088	5551	11752	4471	5664	26.4
4- Low	6325	2065	7392	3768	1067	5
5- Very low	11419	14997	712	17310	-10707	-50
Total Area	30373	30373	30373	30373	$\Sigma = 21415$	100.00

From results presented in Table 15. Shows that a very large extent (70.5% or 21415 km^2) of the soil landscape experienced changes during the period under review. Positive contributions to soil degradation among the sensitivity areas were observed in the following descending manner from highest to lowest; Moderate (26.4%), High (17.8%), Low (5%) and very high (0.8%). A negative contribution of (50%) implying improvement on soil landscape was recorded in the very low sensitivity areas.

In summary the implication of the pattern of contribution of changes recorded in the soil landscape revealed that 50% of the studied landscape recorded soil degradation distributed across the low, moderate, high and very high sensitivity landscape, whereas, the other 50% of the landscape which is the very low sensitivity areas revealed areas that recovered from soil degradation.

Table 16. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on HgSI

Landscape Sensitivity Areas (SA)	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in km^2 1990 (U_{ai})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 2000	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in $Km^2:2020$ (U_{bi})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 based on NDVSI (U_{bi1})	Change in extent of i^{th} SA in Km^2 for study period ($U_{bi}-U_{ai}$)	Proportion of contribution by i^{th} class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	10531	11967	11880	11290	759	32.1
2- High	9504	11597	9805	9285	-219	-9.3
3- Moderate	6368	6370	6345	6710	342	14.5
4- Low	3731	121	2022	2770	-961	-40.7
5- Very low	237	317	321	317	80	3.4
Total Area	30373	30373	30373	30373	$\Sigma = 2361$	100.00

Contributions to desertification in the hydro-geomorphic landscape as presented in Table 16. That only a small extent (2361 km^2 or 7.8%) of the landscape under went changes either positive (degradation) or negative (recovery). Out of this extent that experienced hydro-geomorphological changes the very high sensitivity class contributed 32.1%, while moderate (14.5%) and Very Low (3.4%) of degradation. On the other hand the Low

sensitivity areas contribution rate of (40.7%) was negative and High (9.3%) to represent areas that recovered from soil desiccation, wetland degradation etc.

In summary 50% of the hydro-geomorphic landscape experienced degradation while the other 50% showed recovery from some forms of hydro-geomorphic degradation.

Table 17. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on MCSI

Landscape Sensitivity Areas (SA)	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in km^2 1990 (U_{ai})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 2000	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in $Km^2:2020$ (U_{bi})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 based on NDVSI (U_{bi1})	Change in extent of i^{th} SA in Km^2 for study period ($U_{bi}-U_{ai}$)	Proportion of contribution by i^{th} class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	4740	4489	5033	4348	293	10.1
2- High	5547	9198	6463	6035	916	31.6
3- Moderate	6874	11063	7116	8247	242	8.3
4- Low	8239	4984	7839	5975	-400	-13.8
5- Very low	4973	640	3923	5770	-1050	-36.2
Total Area	30373	30373	30373	30373	$\Sigma = 2901$	100.00

The pattern of contributions of changes in extents in the micro-climatic landscape indicated both positive (degradation and negative (recovery)). Only a small extent of the landscape (2901 km^2 or 9.6%) recorded these various forms of changes. The high sensitivity landscape alone contributed (31.6%) of the areas that

observed degradation, followed by very high 10.1% and Moderate 8.3%. this put together a total of 50% of the landscape recorded degradation as didtributed above. Negative degradation was recorded in the other 50% of the landscape extent with very low landscape contributing (36.2%), Low (13.8%).

Table 18. Proportional Contribution Rate Based on DSI

Landscape Sensitivity Areas (SA)	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in km^2 1990 (U_{ai})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 2000	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in $Km^2:2020$ (U_{bi})	Extent of i^{th} class of SA in Km^2 based on NDVSI (U_{bi1})	Change in extent of i^{th} SA in Km^2 for study period ($U_{bi}-U_{ai}$)	Proportion of contribution by i^{th} class for the period (%)
1-VeryHigh	4740	4489	5033	4348	293	10.1
2- High	5547	9198	6463	6035	916	31.6
3- Moderate	6874	11063	7116	8247	242	8.3
4- Low	8239	4984	7839	5975	-400	-13.8
5- Very low	4973	640	3923	5770	-1050	-36.2
Total Area	30373	30373	30373	30373	$\Sigma = 2901$	100.00

An overview of contribution rate of the overall complex landscape aggregating all of the soil, vegetation, hydro-geomorphic and micro-climatic revealec very striking observations. 50% of the landscape comprising the Very, high and moderate sensitivity areas recorded degradation

of the landscape with the high contributing highest (31.6%), very high (10.1%) and moderate (8.3%). Both low and very low landscape sensitivity areas recorded negative extent of degradation with very low contributing (36.2%) of this extent and low (13.8%).

Table 19. Proportional Contribution Rate of Changes in Extent of Processes and Landscapes

Indicators of desertification processes	Proportional contribution of Change in extent	Proportional contribution rate (%)
NDVI	20725	15.66
APAR	8570	6.47
LSE	17928	13.54
SBI	13525	10.21
SRI	17426	13.16
GSI	22512	17.02

TWI	438	1.22
SPI	126	0.10
STI	5044	3.80
ASI	7108	5.36
LSA	9961	7.52
LST	8923	6.74
Total	132286	100.00
Indicators of Landscapes		
VSI	8923	25.06
SSI	21415	60.15
HgSI	2361	6.63
MCSI	2901	8.15
Total	35600	100.00

From Table 19. It is clearly evident that the major contributions to desertification are observed in the soil and vegetation processes. Among the double digit categories of contribution rate, the highest is GSI (17.02%) followed by NDVI (15.66%), LSE (13.54%), SRI (13.16%) and SBI (10.21%). In the high single digit contributors are LSA (9.52%), LST (6.74%), APAR (5.36%). The least contributors from lowest are SPI (0.1%), TWI (1.22%), STI (3.8%).

Results of contribution rate among the various landscapes that recorded changes in extent are as follows; Highest is SSI (60.15%), followed by VSI (25.06%), the lowest being HgSI (6.63%) and followed by MCSI (8.15%).

In summary the implication of this results indicates the major processes of land degradation or desertification are the soil processes. Similarly the soil landscape is the most altered. The next important sets of desertification processes are vegetation degradation and so the next most altered landscape under desertification. This confirms the assertion by Symeonakis and Drake (2004) that the processes of desertification will penultimately end in vegetation degradation and finally culminate in soil degradation.

Conclusion

Conceptual framework approach adopted in this study proved to be very gainful in determining the proportional contribution rate to extent of desertification by specific biophysical processes,

various landscape sensitivity areas and by different landscape types, soil, vegetation, hydro-geomorphic landforms and micro-climatic or land surface and atmosphere boundary. The study also revealed that the major biophysical processes of desertification are the soil and vegetation degradation. The study affirm the submission by Symeonakis and Drake (2004) that the processes of desertification will penultimately end in vegetation degradation and finally culminate in soil degradation. This is contrary to the view by many that vegetation is the ultimate indicator of desertification effect on the biophysical landscape.

The identification selection of valid and true indicators in this study is very important and has helped not only to identify the severity and proportional contribution rate of desertification processes and landscape changes but also in monitoring and preparation of strong and sustainable action plans to help in land degradation or desertification neutrality and semi-arid land management and restoration.

Recommendation

Many interacting factors affect the ecosystem sustainability and resistance to degradation. Therefore the maintenance of the biotic composition, diversity, and cover is essential to sustainable productivity. In addition to plant factors, maintenance of soil quality processes, including soil texture, nutrient, and biogeochemical cycles, soil microorganisms and biological crust, and resistance to wind and water borne erosion is also essential to sustaining the

health of the ecosystem. To protect arid lands from accelerated desertification and reduce the potential for feedbacks that may accelerate global climate changes, it is important to understand these integrated ecosystem responses and proportional contributions rate of extent individual processes and landscape changes in prioritisation of actions to reverse or neutralise desertification.

References

- Aguilera, H., Castaño, S., Moreno, L., Jiménez-Hernández, M. E., & de la Losa, A. (2013). Model of hydrological behaviour of the anthropized semiarid wetland of Las Tablas de Daimiel National Park (Spain) based on surface water-groundwater interactions. *Hydrogeology Journal*, 21(3), 623–641. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10040-012-0934-4>
- Aguilera, H., Moreno, L., Wesseling, J. G., Jiménez-Hernández, M. E., & Castaño, S. (2016). Soil moisture prediction to support management in semiarid wetlands during drying episodes. *Catena*, 147, 709–724. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2016.07.053>
- An, P., Inanaga, S., Zhu, N., Li, X., Fadul, H. M., & Mars, M. (2007). Plant species as indicators of the extent of desertification in four sandy rangelands. *African Journal of Ecology*, 45(1), 94–102. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2028.2006.00681.x>
- Aranda, V., & Oyonarte, C. (2005). Effect of vegetation with different evolution degree on soil organic matter in a semi-arid environment (Cabo de Gata-Nijar Natural Park, SE Spain). *Journal of Arid Environments*, 62(4), 631–647. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2005.01.004>
- Areola, O. (1982). Soils. In K. M. Barbour et al. (Eds.), *Nigeria in Maps* (pp. 22–23). London: Hodder and Stoughton.
- Barbosa da Silva, F. H., Arieira, J., Parolin, P., Nunes da Cunha, C., & Junk, W. J. (2016). Shrub encroachment influences herbaceous communities in flooded grasslands of a neotropical savanna wetland. *Applied Vegetation Science*, 19(3), 391–400. <https://doi.org/10.1111/avsc.12221>
- Baskan, O., Dengiz, O., & Demirag, İ. T. (2017). The land productivity dynamics trend as a tool for land degradation assessment in a dryland ecosystem. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 189(5), 212. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-017-5909-3>
- Bestelmeyer, B. T., Duniway, M. C., James, D. K., Burkett, L. M., & Havstad, K. M. (2013). A test of critical thresholds and their indicators in a desertification-prone ecosystem: More resilience than we thought. *Ecology Letters*, 16(3), 339–345. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12045>
- Ceccarelli, T., Bajocco, S., Smiraglia, D., Salvati, L., & Perini, L. (2013). Syndromes of land degradation and implications for ecosystem services in Emilia-Romagna, Italy. An evaluation framework for the past and in face of a changing climate. *SISC Conference Proceedings*.
- Cherlet, M., Hutchinson, C., Reynolds, J., Hill, J., Sommer, S., & von Maltitz, G. (Eds.). (2018). *World Atlas of Desertification* (3rd ed.). Luxembourg: Publication Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/9205>
- Dada, R., Kotze, D., Ellery, W., & Uys, M. (2007). WET-RoadMap: A Guide to the Wetland Management Series. WRC Report No. TT 321/07. Water Research Commission, Pretoria.
- Eldridge, D. J., & Soliveres, S. (2014). Are shrubs really a sign of declining ecosystem function? Disentangling the myths and truths of woody encroachment in Australia. *Australian Journal of Botany*, 62(7), 594–608. <https://doi.org/10.1071/BT14137>
- Fabeku, B. B., & Faleyimu, O. I. (2017). Drought Impact Assessment on Vegetation over Sudano-Sahelian Part of Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management*, 21(6), 1135–1142. <https://doi.org/10.4314/jasem.v21i6.20>
- Finlayson, C. M., & Rea, N. (1999). Reasons for the loss and degradation of Australian wetlands. *Wetland Ecology and Management*, 7(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1008468304336>

- Geist, H., & Lambin, E. F. (2006). *Land-Use and Land-Cover Change: Local Processes and Global Impacts*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-32202-7>
- Goldshleger, N., Ben-Dor, E., Benyamini, Y., Agassi, M., & Blumberg, D. G. (2001). Characterization of soil's structural crust by spectral reflectance in the SWIR region. *Terra Nova*, 13(1), 12-17. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-3121.2001.00302.x>
- Hill, J., Stellmes, M., Udelhoven, T., Roder, A., & Sommer, S. (2008). Mediterranean desertification and land degradation: Mapping related land use change syndromes based on satellite observations. *Global and Planetary Change*, 64(3-4), 146-157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2008.10.005>
- Huang, J., Yu, H., Guan, X., Wang, G., & Guo, R. (2016). Accelerated dryland expansion under climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, 6(2), 166-171. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2837>
- Imeson, A. (2012). *Desertification, land degradation and sustainability*. Wiley-Blackwell. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com/books>
- IPBES. (2018a). Summary for policymakers of the assessment report on land degradation and restoration of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. *Ecosystems and People*, 14(1), 44-56. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21513732.2018.1476465>
- Kéfi, S., Alados, C. L., Chaves, R. C. G., Pueyo, Y., & Rietkerk, M. (2010). Is the patch size distribution of vegetation a suitable indicator of desertification processes? Comment. *Ecology*, 91(12), 3739-3742. <https://doi.org/10.1890/09-1915.1>
- Kosmas, C., Ferrara, A., Briassoulis, H., & Imeson, A. (1999). Methodology for mapping Environmentally Sensitive Areas (ESAs) to Desertification. In: Kosmas, C., Kirkby, M., & Geeson, N. (Eds.), *The Medalus project: Mediterranean desertification and land use. Manual on key indicators of desertification and mapping environmentally sensitive areas to desertification* (pp. 31-47). European Union. ISBN 92-828-6349-2
- Kosmas, C., Kairis, O., Karavitis, C., Acikalin, S., Alcalá, M., Alfama, P., ... & Salvati, L. (2015). An exploratory analysis of land abandonment drivers in areas prone to desertification. *Catena*, 128, 256-261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2015.02.010>
- Maestre, F. T., & Escudero, A. (2009). Is the patch size distribution of vegetation a suitable indicator of desertification processes? *Ecology*, 90(7), 1729-1735. <https://doi.org/10.1890/08-2096.1>
- Maxwell-Borjor Achuk Eba. (2020). A critique of Aldo Leopold's land ethic for environmental management. *Jurnal Office: Jurnal Pemikiran Ilmiah dan Pendidikan Administrasi Perkantoran*, 6(2), 131-142. <https://doi.org/10.26858/jo.v6i2.13382>
- Medugu, N. I., Rafee, M., & Johar, M. F. (2011). Drought and desertification management in arid and semi-arid zones of Northern Nigeria. *Environmental Quality Management*, 22(5), 595-611. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tqem.20288>
- Naidu, L. G. K., Dharumarajan, S., Lalitha, M., Srinivas, S., Ramamurthy, V., & Singh, S. K. (2014). Categorisation and delineation of prime and marginal lands of Andhra Pradesh for different uses. *Agropedology*, 24, 253-261.
- Nkonya, E., Gerber, N., von Braun, J., & De Pinto, A. (2011). *Economics of Land Degradation: The Costs of Action versus Inaction*. International Food Policy Research Institute, IFPRI, Issue Brief 68.
- Osaigbovo, A. C. (2000). *Regional Geography of Nigeria*. Lagos: Nimbo Books. Chapter 4.
- Parry, J. T. (1996). Land degradation in the tropics: Environmental and policy issues. In Eden, M. J., & Parry, J. T. (Eds.), *Land degradation in the tropics: Environmental and policy issues* (pp. 91-97). London: Pinter.
- Piao, S., Yin, G., Tan, J., Cheng, L., Huang, M., Li, Y., ... & Wang, Y. (2015). Detection and attribution of vegetation greening trend in China over the last 30 years. *Global Change Biology*, 21(4), 1601-1609. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12795>

- Prince, S. D. (2016). Where does desertification occur? Mapping dryland degradation at regional to global scales. In: Behnke, R. H., & Mortimore, M. (Eds.), *The end of desertification? Disputing environmental change in the drylands* (pp. 225-263). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-16014-1_9
- Rajan, K., Natarajan, A., Anil Kumar, K. S., Badrinath, M. S., & Gowda, R. C. (2010). Soil organic carbon: The most reliable indicator for monitoring land degradation by soil erosion. *Current Science*, 99(6), 823-827.
- Reynolds, J. F., & Stafford Smith, D. M. (2002). *Global desertification: Do humans cause deserts?* Dahlem University Press.
- Reynolds, J. F., Kemp, P. R., Ogle, K., & Fernandez, R. J. (2004). Modifying the pulse-reserve paradigm for deserts of North America: Precipitation pulses, soil water, and plant responses. *Oecologia*, 141(2), 194-210. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-004-1520-4>
- Salvati, L., & Zitti, M. (2008). Assessing the impact of ecological and economic factors on land degradation vulnerability through multiway analysis. *Ecological Indicators*, 9(2), 357-363. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2008.05.006>
- Salvati, L., Mancini, A., Bajocco, S., & Munafò, M. (2011). Socioeconomic development and vulnerability to land degradation in Italy. *Regional Environmental Change*, 11(4), 767-777. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-011-0209-x>
- Schellnhuber, H. J., Block, A., Cassel-Gintz, M., Kropp, J., Lammel, G., Lass, W., ... & Reusswig, F. (1997). Syndromes of global change. *GAI*, 6(1), 19-34.
- Sillitoe, P. (2006). Ethnobiology and applied anthropology: Rapprochement of the academic with the practical. *Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute*, 12(1), 119-142. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9655.2006.00283.x>
- Thomas, D. S. G., & Middleton, N. J. (1994). Desertification: Exploding the myth. *Global Environmental Change*, 4(1), 3-8. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0959-3780\(94\)90016-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0959-3780(94)90016-7)
- Thornes, J. B. (1996). *Desertification in the Mediterranean*. In: Brandt, J., & Thornes, J. (Eds.), *Mediterranean desertification and land use* (pp. 23-36). Wiley.
- Törnros, T., & Menzel, L. (2014). Addressing drought conditions under current and future climates in the Jordan River region. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 18(1), 305-318. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-18-305-2014>
- UNEP. (1994). *United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification in Those Countries Experiencing Serious Drought and/or Desertification, Particularly in Africa*. United Nations Environment Programme. Retrieved from https://www.unccd.int/sites/default/files/relevant-links/2017-01/UNCCD_Convention_ENG.pdf
- UNCCD. (2013). *A Stronger UNCCD for a Land-Degradation Neutral World*. United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification.
- Verstraete, M. M., & Scholes, R. J. (2001). Biophysical and environmental aspects of desertification. *Land Degradation & Development*, 12(1), 71-83. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.458>
- Wang, X., Chen, F., & Dong, Z. (2006). The relative role of climatic and human factors in desertification in semiarid China. *Global Environmental Change*, 16(1), 48-57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2005.06.006>
- Warren, A. (2002). Land degradation is contextual. *Land Degradation & Development*, 13(6), 449-459. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.532>
- White, R., & Nackoney, J. (2003). *Human population and the extinction of biodiversity*. Encyclopedia of Life Support Systems (EOLSS), UNESCO.
- Zdruli, P. (2014). Land resources of the Mediterranean: Status, pressures, trends and impacts on future regional development. *Land Degradation & Development*, 25(4), 373-384. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2150>